

WHO IS THE HOLY SPIRIT?

By

Prasanna Kumar Monditoka

INTRODUCTION

Christians believe that there are three distinct persons in the Godhead—Father, Son, and the Spirit. However, there has been much misunderstanding on the person, nature, and work of the Holy Spirit. Some religious sects disregard the person and nature of the Holy Spirit by limiting him to power. Some Christians articulate that the Holy Spirit is the spirit of God or the Spirit of Christ. They undermine his distinctive personhood and work by absorbing him into the nature and work of the trinity.¹ Who is the Holy Spirit? How can we understand his personhood and work in relation to the Father and the Son? Should we understand him only as a subordinate and helper of the Father and the Son?

In this article, the Holy Spirit is not considered merely as a power, rather, he is a distinct person in the Godhead with distinctive personhood, mission, and work of appropriation within the trinity. The orthodox understanding of the identity, person, and work of the Holy Spirit in distinction and in relation to God the Father and God the Son in a trinitarian model is defended. First, some incorrect notions such as the Holy Spirit as a Power, Spirit of God, and Spirit of Christ are discussed. Second, the orthodox position with biblical and theological justification will be explained along with the evidence from philosophical arguments and ecumenical affirmations. The argumentation from the Old Testament and the New Testament and

¹ John Webster, “The identity of the Holy Spirit: A problem in Trinitarian theology,” *Themelios* 9, no. 1 (1983): 4.

the theological coherence of the doctrine will be explained. The philosophical consistency of the orthodox argument is explained in contrast to the incorrect assumptions. The orthodox position is supported by the writings of the church fathers and ecumenical councils. The common objections against the orthodox doctrine of the Holy Spirit is discussed.

Positions on the Issue

Holy Spirit is a Power

Jehovah's witnesses suggest that the Holy Spirit is God's power in action, it is his active force. They contend that God sends out his Spirit by sending his energy to carry out his will. Bible refers to the spirit as God's hands, fingers, or breath. The Holy Spirit operates only as directed by God just like hands which cannot function independently from mind and body. Bible likens Holy Spirit to water; therefore, it is impersonal.² The Bible designates God the Father with the title Jehovah and His Son with the title Jesus Christ. However, Bible never designates a proper name to the Holy Spirit. When Stephen was martyred, he was filled with the Holy Spirit, he saw two persons God and Jesus, but he never saw the Holy Spirit. Therefore, the Holy Spirit is not a person.³

Jehovah's Witnesses attempted to correct the orthodox misconceptions about the Holy Spirit. They argue that the reference to the trinity in 1 John 5:7-8 was spurious and not part of the original manuscripts. We should not infer the personification of the Spirit to the personhood. Bible personifies things like sin, death, and wisdom. John used a neuter noun *pneuma* to refer to

² Watchtower Bible and Tract Society of New York, *Aid to Bible Understanding: Containing Historical, Geographical, Religious, and, Social Facts Concerning Bible Persons, Peoples, Places, Plant and Animal Life, Activities, and so Forth* (New York: Watchtower Bible and Tract Society of New York, 1971), 1542.

³ Watchtower Bible and Tract Society of New York, *Aid to Bible Understanding*, 1543-1544.

the Holy Spirit and used a genderless pronoun “it” (John 14:16-17). The baptism in the name of the Holy Spirit does not prove that it is a person. Bible sometimes uses “name” to refer to power or authority. The person who is baptized in the Spirit recognizes the power and role of the Spirit in fulfilling God’s will. Apostles and early disciples did not believe that the Holy Spirit is a person. The Holy Spirit was identified as a person at the Council of Constantinople in AD 381.⁴

In a similar vein, Christadelphians argue that the Spirit is not a separate person. The Holy Spirit is God’s own radiant power which outflows from him and makes his presence everywhere. The Spirit is not personal in the sense that it is a distinct person in the Godhead, but the spirit is personal in that it is of God himself.⁵ They argue that that the term God the Holy Spirit is not found in the Bible. It is God’s power in creation. God executes his plans by his almighty power the Holy Spirit (John 4:24). God does everything by his Spirit, and he fills his creation with his Spirit. He sustains everything by his wise and sustaining Spirit.⁶

God as Spirit

Professor Geoffrey Lampe proposed that “Spirit” in the Bible does not refer to a divine person, but the whole activity of God in relation to man. In other words, the Spirit of God does not refer to a divine hypostasis distinct from God the Father and God the Son, but as representing God himself as active towards and in his human creation. God revealed and experienced as Spirit in his personal outreach. In Jesus, the original God’s plan for human relationship was fully

⁴ Jehovah’s Witnesses, “What is the Holy Spirit?” last accessed October 05, 2021, <https://www.jw.org/en/bible-teachings/questions/what-is-the-holy-spirit/>.

⁵ David V. Barrett, *Sects, Cults, and Alternative Religions: A World Survey and Sourcebook* (London: Blandford, 1996), 75-76.

⁶ Christadelphia, “The Holy Spirit: Bible Understanding of God’s Power,” last accessed October 05, 2021, <http://www.christadelphia.org/pamphlet/holysprt.php>.

realized because God inhabited and inspired the human spirit of Jesus. God worked decisively to cause men to share in a relationship with God.⁷

Lampe provided a semantic, biblical, and theological explanation for his view. He argues that in the Hebrew language, the word ‘Sprit’ is a ‘bridge’ word to express God’s outreach towards, and contact with, the created world. These terms connect God’s transcendent identity with his immanent activities in relating with his creation in time and space.⁸ In the Old Testament, God’s Spirit is identified with his wisdom, and it was personified. However, he argued that the Wisdom-Spirit is a symbolical depiction of God’s work, it is not intended to be interpreted as a distinct being.⁹ Lampe extended his argument by unifying the Spirit of God and Spirit of Christ. The Spirit reaches to Christians as the Spirit of Jesus. The believers in Christ share his life of sonship, the life of man in his true relationship with God. According to Luke’s Gospel, the Spirit in the church’s mission is the same Spirit that rested upon Jesus.¹⁰ The baptism into the one body and one spirit depicts the truth of becoming one man in Christ Jesus. God unites us with Christ by sending the Spirit into our hearts and enabling us to cry ‘Abba, Father.’ The Spirit of Jesus establishes a new relationship of grace and truth between man and God.¹¹ Lampe summarizes his position as follows:

We are using the word ‘Spirit’ to speak of God as active and as related to personal beings, which is the only way in which we can speak of God, since this is how he discloses himself to us and we can know nothing about God which he does not reveal.... In speaking now of God as Spirit we are not referring to an impersonal influence, an energy transmitted by God but distinct from himself. Nor are we indicating a divine entity or hypostasis which is a

⁷ G. W. H. Lampe, *God as Spirit*. The Bampton Lectures, 1976, (Oxford England: Clarendon Press, 1977), 11.

⁸ Lampe, 35.

⁹ Lampe, 42.

¹⁰ Lampe, 70.

¹¹ Lampe, 75.

third person of the Godhead. We are speaking of God himself, his personal presence, as active and related.¹²

Therefore, according to Lampe, the Spirit is not an impersonal energy or force, rather, it is God who is actively involving and relating himself to humans as Spirit.

Spirit of Christ

The protestant theologies of the Holy Spirit in agreement with patristic theology maintained a very close association between the doctrine of the Holy Spirit and the person of Christ. The cosmic and general features of the Spirit were neglected due to the rejection of natural theology.¹³ The revelatory knowledge of God is accessible only in Christ and there is no presence of God outside of him. We should not speak the work of the Spirit in the world as if the incarnation had not taken place. There was much emphasis on the Christological context of the Spirit within the trinity.¹⁴

Karl Barth argued that the Holy Spirit is the power of God, inseparably linked to his Word, which goes out to draw men to the Word.¹⁵ Barth affirms that the very union between humanity and God is the Holy Spirit. Through the Spirit, flesh and blood unite with Jesus Christ.¹⁶ The identity of the Spirit is confined by his role in uniting the believer with Christ. The Spirit acts as an agent in applying Christ's accomplishment of salvation. The Spirit of Christ reveals his words and deeds, his cross, and resurrection to the believers. He helps us to participate in the word and deed of Christ. The work of Spirit is marked by his relation to Christ.

¹² Lampe, 208.

¹³ John Webster, "The identity of the Holy Spirit: A problem in Trinitarian theology," *Themelios* 9, no. 1 (1983): 5-6.

¹⁴ Webster, 5-6.

¹⁵ Philip J. Rosato, *The Spirit as Lord: The Pneumatology of Karl Barth* (Edinburgh: T&T Clark, 1981), 47.

¹⁶ Rosato, 68.

He produces Christ's pattern of death and resurrection in Christians to confirm them in baptism and sanctification. The subservient and instrumental work of the Spirit to the work of the incarnate Son undermines his place within the trinity. If the Spirit has been envisioned only as a bond of love between the Father and Son, it is difficult to distinguish his personhood from the first two persons.¹⁷

Traditional Trinitarian View of the Holy Spirit

The traditional view of the church affirmed that the Holy Spirit is the third person of the Trinity, fully God and coequal with other persons of the trinity— God the Father and God the Son.¹⁸ The Holy Spirit is distinguished by his eternal procession. He eternally proceeds from the Father and the Son.¹⁹ The Holy Spirit operates inseparably with the Father and the Son. However, there are particular divine works— speaking, creating, recreating, and perfecting— that are appropriated to and terminated in, the Holy Spirit.²⁰

Gregg R. Allison and Andreas J. Köstenberger provided a helpful summary of the traditional trinitarian view of the Nicene-Constantinopolitan Creed (AD 381) and the *filioque* clause from the Synod of Toledo (589) of the Holy Spirit as follows:

“... (1) The Holy Spirit is God, being called “the Lord” and, together with God the Father and God the Son, being the object of the worship and adoration. (2) The Holy Spirit is a divine Person, the Third Person of the Trinity, proceeding from both the person of the Father and the person of the Son. (3) Two major works in which the Holy Spirit (without separation from the Father and the Son) is involved are as the Giver of life”—creation/re-creation/perfection—and as the one who spoke by the prophets—revelation—with particular reference to the Scripture, the written Word of the

¹⁷ Webster, 5-6.

¹⁸ Gregg R Allison and Wayne A Grudem, *Historical Theology: An Introduction to Christian Doctrine: A Companion to Wayne Grudem's Systematic Theology*. (Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 2011), 430.

¹⁹ Gregg R. Allison and Andreas J. Köstenberger, *The Holy Spirit: Theology for the People of God* (Nashville, Tennessee: B&H Academic, 2020), 256.

²⁰ Allison and Köstenberger, *The Holy Spirit*, 295.

triune God. These works also demonstrate the divine personhood of the Spirit, which the church confesses.²¹

Therefore, the Holy Spirit is not a power, nor merely a spirit of God or Son; rather, he is the third person of the Trinity with a distinct relation to the Father and the Son.

Biblical and Theological Justification

First, the Bible affirms that the Holy Spirit is God — together with the Father and the Son. The scripture parallels and relates the person and work of the Holy Spirit to the person and work of God in the New Testament and the Old Testament. In Acts 5:3-4, Ananias and Sapphira were lied to the Holy Spirit, and it was considered as a lie to God (Exod 17:2; Deut 6:16).²² The Holy Spirit possesses and exhibits the divine attributes of God. He is omnipresent (Ps 139:7-10), omniscient (Isa 40:13-14, John 16:13, and 1 Cor 2:10-11), omnipotent in effectuating the incarnation of Christ (Luke 1:34-37), and he is eternal (Heb 9:14). The Holy Spirit involves in and performs divine works.²³ He was involved in creation (Gen 1:2), sustains life (Job 33:4, Ps 104:27-30), regenerates sinners (John 3:5-6), joins believers to Christ (Rom 8:9-10), justifies and sanctifies (1 Cor 6:11), and effectuates consummation (Rom 8:11). The doctrine of the Trinity affirms of the divinity of the Holy Spirit (Gen 2:7, Job 33:4, Ps 33:6, Matt 3:16-17, John 1:1-3, Gal 4:4-6, and Col 1:15-20).²⁴

Second, the Holy Spirit is a distinct person in relation to the Father and Son in the Trinity. He eternally proceeds from the Father and the Son.²⁵ This hypostatic dimension of the Spirit rejects the notion of the impersonal nature of the Spirit. John F. Frame argues that the

²¹ Allison and Köstenberger, *The Holy Spirit*, 237.

²² Allison and Köstenberger, *The Holy Spirit*, 239-240.

²³ Allison and Köstenberger, *The Holy Spirit*, 240.

²⁴ Allison and Köstenberger, *The Holy Spirit*, 240-241.

²⁵ Allison and Köstsenberger, *The Holy Spirit*, 256.

Spirit is not merely an impersonal power; rather, he is a personal bearer of divine power. The Spirit represents God's wisdom (Ex 28:3, 31:3, Luke 1:17, Eph 1:17) and the Spirit has mind (Rom 8:27). The works of the Holy Spirit reveal his personal nature. He comforts, inspires, speaks, witnesses, hears, sends, knows, teaches, guides, and intercedes for the believers. Frame also suggested possible explanations for biblical phrases like "Spirit of Christ" and "life-giving Spirit." He argued that Christ completes his work by the special gift of the Spirit (Isa 61:1, Matt 3:16, Luke 4:18) and that the Spirit testifies Christ (John 15:26). The Spirit and Christ are intimately involved in giving life to believers. He argues that the phrases themselves bear witness that they are distinct.²⁶

Third, the Holy Spirit performs his works inseparably with the Father and the Son; yet some of the divine works are terminated in or appropriated to the Holy Spirit.²⁷ Since the triune God is one, he has one will, one power, and one purpose and his operations are inseparable. All things originate from him, consist through him, and realize their purpose in him.²⁸ In spite of the inseparable operations of one triune God, certain divine acts are appropriated to one of the three persons as they reach their final purpose in that person. It is proper to say that certain divine works —speaking, creating, re-creating, perfecting, and filling with the presence of triune God—are appropriated to the Holy Spirit. In addition, all divine works terminate in the Spirit as he is the perfecting cause.²⁹ This robust understanding of the person and work of the Holy Spirit helps to avoid false notions of Spirit of God or Christ.

²⁶ John M. Frame, *The Doctrine of God. A Theology of Lordship* (Phillipsburg, NJ: P&R Pub, 2002), 691-693.

²⁷ Allison and Köstenberger, *The Holy Spirit*, 295.

²⁸ Allison and Köstenberger, *The Holy Spirit*, 277-278.

²⁹ Allison and Köstenberger, *The Holy Spirit*, 284.

Philosophical Justification

The affirmation of the Holy Spirit as the divine person of the Trinity needs to be justified philosophically. First, the Holy Spirit eternally proceeds from the Father and the Son. The Son eternally generates from the Father. However, the generation of the Son and the procession of the Spirit are internal to God. The Holy Spirit is the third member of the trinity—after the Father and the Son. However, it does not diminish his divinity, nor limits him to inferior power. The three persons of the trinity share the same divine power, will, and purpose.³⁰ Second, the Holy Spirit along with other two persons subsist in the one Godhead. When three persons are distinguished, they are distinguished only in relation to each other. There is no separation of the Father, Son, and the Spirit in Godhead.³¹

Ecumenical Affirmation

The early church suffered attacks from different heresies which undermined the divinity of the Son and the Spirit. The traditional view of the Spirit was challenged by two heretic movements—dynamic Monarchianism and modalistic Monarchianism. The proponents of dynamic Monarchianism taught that the Holy Spirit is a divine influence. On the other hand, the proponents of modalistic Monarchianism taught that there is one God who can be called by three different names—Father, Son, and Spirit.³²

In response to the heresies, the early church fathers and the ecumenical councils upheld and defended the traditional the doctrine of the trinity. First, Tertullian refuted the view of Monarchianism and championed the traditional trinitarian view. He argued that “...the Son is not by generation separated from the Father, seeing that the Holy Trinity are three “not by diversity

³⁰ Christopher R. J. Holmes, *The Holy Spirit. New Studies in Dogmatics*, ed. Michael Allen and Scott R. Swain (Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 2015), 99.

³¹ Holmes, *The Holy Spirit*, 65.

³² Allison and Grudem, *Historical Theology*, 433.

but by distribution, not by division but by distinction.”³³ He also argued that to reject the Son and the Spirit is to reject the Father.³⁴ Similarly, Athanasius pointed out that the Son and the Spirit are not merely creatures.³⁵ He argued that the father creates all things through the Son and the Holy Spirit. He insisted that the Catholic church always affirmed the unity and indivisibility of the Trinity.³⁶ The church officially declared the divinity, person, and work of the Holy Spirit at the Council of Constantinople, in 381.³⁷

Objections

First, some theologians argue that we do not know much about God because of his ineffability (unknowability). They argue that since God is transcendent and wholly other, we should not make universal claims about God. It is agreed that we cannot fully comprehend God and the mystery of the Trinity. However, this argument cannot undermine the fact that God has revealed himself in his word.³⁸

Second, some theologians reject the eternal procession of the Spirit. They argue that the Father sent the Spirit only at the Pentecost; it is not eternal procession. It is agreed that eternal relations cannot be fully understood based on temporal missions. However, it is

³³ Tertullian, *Adversus Praxean: Tertullian's Treatise against Praxeas*, trans. Ernest Evans (London: SPCK, 1948), 21-22.

³⁴ Tertullian, 21-22.

³⁵ Athanasius and Didymus. *Works on the Spirit: Athanasius's Letters to Serapion on the Holy Spirit, and, Didymus's on the Holy Spirit*. trans. DelCogliano, Mark, Andrew Radde-Gallwitz, and Lewis Ayres, Popular Patristics Series, No. 43. (Yonkers, NY: St. Vladimir's Seminary Press, 2011), 119-120.

³⁶ Athanasius and Didymus, 123-125.

³⁷ Allison and Grudem, *Historical Theology*, 437.

³⁸ Frame, *The Doctrine of God*, 705.

reasonable to recognize the eternal relations based on the revealed temporal relations in God's word.³⁹

Conclusion

In this article, the traditional trinitarian view of the Holy Spirit was defended with the help of biblical, theological, philosophical, and ecumenical evidence. The traditional view affirmed that the Holy Spirit is the third person of the Trinity, fully God and coequal with other persons of the trinity— God the Father and God the Son.⁴⁰ The Holy Spirit is a distinct person in relation to the Father and Son in the Trinity. He eternally proceeds from the Father and the Son.⁴¹ It is proper to say that certain divine works —speaking, creating, re-creating, perfecting, and filling with the presence of triune God —are appropriated to the Holy Spirit. In addition, all divine works terminate in the Spirit as he is the perfecting cause.⁴² This robust understanding of the person and work of the Holy Spirit helps to avoid false notions of the Spirit—Spirit of God or Christ.

³⁹ Matthew Barrett, *Simply Trinity: The Unmanipulated Father, Son, and Spirit* (Grand Rapids, MI: Baker Publishing Group, 2021), 270-271.

⁴⁰ Allison and Grudem, *Historical Theology*, 430.

⁴¹ Allison and Köstsenberger, *The Holy Spirit*, 256.

⁴² Allison and Köstsenberger, *The Holy Spirit*, 284.

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